

Quantum Wavefunction as a Steady Stream Picture and Entropy

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In (1) the Wigner transform of an oscillator is calculated and the high n energy level limit taken using the WKB approximation yielding a result proportional to $\delta(p - p(x)) + \delta(p + p(x))$ where $p(x) = \sqrt{2m(E - \frac{1}{2}kx^2)}$. The Wigner transform involves quantum wavefunctions which for bound systems include $\pm p$ components which interfere i.e. $a(p)(\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx))$ for $a(p) = a(-p)$. Classically, a bound particle moves to the right during one time interval and to the left during the other so there is no interference of $\pm p$. The quantum wavefunction retains $\pm p$ interference for all energy levels and so does not portray the full physical information of the bound system i.e. leads to the two delta functions.

For high n (energy level), crests and troughs are very narrow compared to the length of the system, approximating dx units of length. Thus, uncertainty in time is only within these tiny crests/troughs, otherwise there is a distinct time position relationship as in classical physics, but the wavefunction $W(x)$ does not show it. How then may the wavefunction be interpreted? We argue the time independent wavefunction, say for a bound state, represents an averaged steady stream picture which is often not the physical picture. For example, a bound particle is not a steady stream average nor is a finite number of photons hitting an interface of media with different indices of refraction/reflection. Nevertheless, the steady stream approach with time removed may be used to solve the problem i.e. ultimately find a one dimensional spatial density (which averages out the original two dimensional probability of $\exp(ipx)$, energy levels etc. For instance, the energy levels of a bound system do not depend on following the particle in time.

We raise this issue because we think it may have implications on the calculation of entropy in bound single particle quantum systems. In general, a spatial Shannon's entropy is defined as: $-W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)W(x)]$ (one dimensional problem). $W(x)$ (wavefunction) is real because p/p pieces interfere in a steady stream picture. A single bound particle, however, is not a steady stream picture. $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamic probability equal to $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ to indicate the direction of motion. Simply because $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ removes the complex portion (i.e. for a steady state picture with $a(p) = a(-p)$) does not mean that this represents the full physical picture especially as energy levels become high and crests/troughs become narrower with respect to the overall system length it seems there is no justification for the steady stream interference picture.. In other words, using a real $W(x)$ in a Shannon's entropy expression treats one dimensional probability $W(x) =$ bound wavefunction, but this is not the full probability in the picture, we argue. Full probability is two dimensional and demonstrates direction for many energy levels (especially high ones). For a free particle $\exp(ipx)$, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are essentially the same distribution. Thus $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ describes the probability distribution in x . For $W_1(x) = \sum_{p>0} a(p)\exp(ipx)$, $\text{Real}(W_1(x))$ is not equal to $\text{Imaginary}(W_1(x))$ because one does not have a simple shift of the real distribution to obtain the imaginary one. The real distribution is chosen to represent probability because the interference of $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ terms removes the imaginary piece, but it is removed only on average. If physically $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ should not interfere, then one may need to take some kind of average of $\text{Real}(W_1(x))\text{Real}(W_1(x))$ and $\text{Imaginary}(W_1(x))\text{Imaginary}(W_1(x))$ and use this in Shannon's entropy.

Quantum Wavefunction and Bound State

The time-independent Schrodinger equation (nonrelativistic case) may be used to find the energy levels of a quantum single particle bound system. It may be noted that the kinetic energy is the same for a particle with $+p$ and $-p$ even for quantum free particles. Interference of different free particle wavefunctions occurs within a bound state wavefunction i.e.

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

Classically a bound particle moves to the right half of the time and to the left the other half. $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamical probability (i.e. two dimensional to indicate the direction of motion), with \hbar/p being a wavelength. If the wavelength is of the order of the physical system, the particle may be anywhere within the wavelength region, but $\exp(ipx)$ may not be the only wavefunction present, $\exp(-ipx)$ could also be present because one cannot follow the particle in time within a wavelength region. Thus there is interference $a(p) [\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)]$ which removes the second dimension of probability. This is fine if the wavelength is of the order of the length between the classical turning points. If, however, $W(x)$ starts to exhibit crests/troughs at a certain energy level which are small with respect to the system length then the particle is localized within these crests. There is no reason to believe that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ should interfere unless one considers a steady stream picture, which may be fine for an average energy calculation. The time-independent Schrodinger equation is an example. The $\exp(-iE_n t)$ factor is not linked with motion of a particle in time. For any energy level, the time-independent Schrodinger equation is equivalent to the classical energy conservation result:

$$KE_{\text{classical}}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2)) \text{ with } KE_{\text{classical}}(x) = \{-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W\}$$

Classically, however, the particle moves either to the left or right and this physical reality is not present, it seems, in the quantum wavefunction which still retains $\pm p$ interference at high n (energy level). As a result, one might suggest that a quantum wavefunction represents a steady state picture which is useful for calculating certain quantities like energy, but is not the full physical picture. We give a second example of this issue.

Reflection/Refraction of Photons

One may consider a single photon which travels along x and strikes the interface of two media with different indices of refraction. There is a probability to reflect and to refract. Physically, this is not a steady stream picture. Nevertheless, steady stream analysis with time removed may be used to calculate the probabilities of the single photon problem. In such a case, the incident photon $A \exp(ipx)$ interferes with the reflected photon $B \exp(-ipx)$ and this value matches $C \exp(i$

$p^2 x$) of the refracted photon. Matching is done at the interface which may be taken at $x=0$. One may match wavefunctions and their first derivatives. One may argue that one does not follow motion in time within a wavelength so that within a wavelength \hbar/p of the interface or beyond it, one does not really know if one has the incident photon, reflected or refracted one even in the single photon case. This uncertainty may be fine near the interface, but not away from it for a single photon. If one uses a steady stream picture, however, interference occurs everywhere i.e. $A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx)$.

Possible Issue with the Steady Stream Picture

If the steady stream picture, i.e. one of interference of p and $-p$ wavefunctions, for all n correctly solves for all energy levels, one may ask: Is there a potential problem with using a steady stream picture when this is not actually the physical picture? We suggest that there may possibly be an issue with the calculation of the spatial Shannon's entropy:

$$S = - \int dx W(x) \ln [W(x)] \quad ((3))$$

$W(x)$ is a steady stream density which does not separate forward motion from backwards motion at any energy level. For high energy levels this makes comparisons with classical physics problematic as there is distinct right and left motion at different times classically. As humps in $W(x)$ become small with respect to the system length (i.e. distance between classical turning points), the particle seems to be localized within the humps and it seems actual motion should either be to the right or left. Thus interference removes the two dimensional behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(i p(x) x)$ in the WKB approximation. As a result, $W(x)$ within a hump might not be fully meaningful. $W(x)$ is fine for energy calculations as $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ represent the same kinetic energy if $a(p)=a(-p)$. Furthermore, for low energy levels there is reason to have $p, -p$ interfere because the wavelength is of the order of the system length. For higher energy levels, however, it is not clear why $p, -p$ should interfere to remove the imaginary part of the distribution:

$$\sum_{p>0} a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{In general: } \text{Real}\{\sum_{p>0} a(p) \exp(ipx)\} \text{ may not equal } \text{Imaginary}\{\sum_{p>0} a(p) \exp(ipx)\} \quad ((5))$$

For example,, consider $W(x) = \text{Real}\{\sum_{p>0} a(p) \exp(ipx)\} = \sum_{p>0} a(p) \cos(px)$. Then $\int dx W(x) \cos(px) = a(p)$. If $\text{Imaginary}\{\sum_{p>0} a(p) \exp(ipx)\} = W(x+b)$ where b is a shift, then: $\int dx W(x+b) \cos(px) = a(p)$ and $b = 3.14 / (2p)$. Thus b is p specific and not a constant shift

If this is the case, then there are two probability distributions, which are not the spatial shift of each other, which are associated with a quantum particle, but $W(x)W(x)$ (for say $W(x)$ even), only takes the real part. $\text{Imaginary}\{\sum_{p>0} a(p) \exp(ipx)\}$ does not appear in the Schrodinger equation because it is not linked with kinetic energy. The kinetic energies

associated with $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are equal, but the imaginary parts of probability cancel for $a(p)=a(-p)$.

As a result, we argue that $W(x)W(x)$ may not represent the full spatial probability density associated with entropy even though it represents a steady stream density. It may be necessary to take an average of:

$$\text{Real}\{\text{Sum over } p>0 a(p)\exp(ipx)\}\text{Real}\{\text{Sum over } p>0 a(p)\exp(ipx)\} \text{ and } \text{Imaginary}\{\text{Sum over } p>0 a(p)\exp(ipx)\}\text{Imaginary}\{\text{Sum over } p>0 a(p)\exp(ipx)\} \quad ((5))$$

to obtain a density which might apply to a non-steady stream situation.

For very high energy levels, peaks become very sharp and a single $\exp(ipx)$ dominates the Sum over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ in each tiny dx region (the size of the peak of $W(x)$). In that case, $\text{Real}(\exp(ipx)) = \cos(px)$ where $p=p(x)=\sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}$ and $\text{Im}(\exp(ipx)) = \sin(px)$ and the two distributions are spatial shifts of each other.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a quantum wavefunction for a bound system involves interference of p , $-p$ pieces i.e $a(p)\exp(ipx)$, $a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ pieces for all energy levels. If $a(p)=a(-p)$ the imaginary part of the wavefunction cancels, but we argue it does not disappear, it only cancels on average. As energy increases, humps in $W(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)$ =wavefunction) become smaller in their x range and the particle becomes more localized to x regions. In such a case, we argue there should be distinct forwards and backwards motion as in the classical case, but the wavefunction, which represents a kind of steady stream picture, does not separate the two motions for any energy level. If one wishes to calculate the energy using the time-independent Schrodinger equation this is not a problem as $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ represent the same kinetic energy (with $a(p)=a(-p)$). Even $W(x)W(x)$ = spatial density may be linked to experimental results which sample both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$.

We argue, however, that physically there is motion to the right and left in a bound problem and that for high energy levels (but not at the WKB limit), Shannon's entropy using $W(x)W(x)$ may not be the full picture. For an even $W(x)$, $W(x)=W_1(x) = \text{Real Sum over } p>0 a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but $\text{Imaginary Sum over } p>0 a(p)\exp(ipx)$ exists and should be considered as there are two pieces to the spatial wavelength for motion in one direction. Thus $(\text{Real } W_1)(\text{Real } W_1)$ and $(\text{Im } W_1)(\text{Im } W_1)$ represent two different distributions (not simply shifted in space) which might need to be averaged in order to obtain an appropriate spatial density to use in Shannon's entropy expression.

References

1. Mostowski J. and Pietraszewicz, J. Wigner Function for Harmonic Oscillator and the Classical Limit (2021) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2104.06638.pdf>